

Table S3: Acrophase analyses of stridulation and locomotion activity of individual crickets from the four experimental treatments. Only animals whose activity period was found significant were included in the acrophase analysis. Each datapoint represents the acrophase calculated for five days. The difference data was calculated by subtracting locomotion values from stridulation values of the same individual. Data are presented for all individuals, and separately for those cases where data for both behaviors was available for the same individual.

		Treatment	N	Mean (°)	Vector Length	Median (°)	Variance (°)	Circular SD (°)	SE (°)	95% CI (+/-)
All individuals	Stridulation	LD	15	282.2	0.807	278.4	0.193	37.5	10.6	20.87
		LL ₂	19	258.4	0.404	238.0	0.596	77.2	22.0	43.16
		LL ₅	18	268.8	0.421	274.4	0.579	75.4	21.6	42.37
		LL	17	18.1	0.303	20.0	0.697	88.5	31.7	62.05
	Locomotion	LD	11	87.3	0.673	87.0	0.327	51.0	15.9	31.16
		LL ₂	25	94.9	0.748	100.7	0.252	43.7	8.7	16.97
		LL ₅	13	73.9	0.472	71.9	0.528	70.2	24.0	47.11
		LL	24	4.5	0.255	18.6	0.745	94.8	31.9	62.59
Data for same individuals only	Stridulation	LD	10	278.6	0.93	275.1	0.07	21.8	8.1	15.90
		LL ₂	19	251.8	0.404	231.5	0.596	77.1	22.0	43.11
		LL ₅	9	267.1	0.54	268.3	0.46	63.6	24.7	48.35
		LL	10	355.7	0.41	3.1	0.59	76.5	34.4	67.40
	Locomotion	LD	10	74.0	0.689	84.1	0.311	49.5	16.1	31.59
		LL ₂	19	82.5	0.799	92.1	0.201	38.4	8.7	17.07
		LL ₅	9	77.3	0.462	107.2	0.538	71.2	30.9	60.63
		LL	10	14.6	0.561	17.1	0.439	61.6	22.0	43.09
	Difference	LD	10	209.1	0.644	198.9	0.356	53.7	17.9	35.12
		LL ₂	19	124.9	0.276	127.9	0.724	91.9	33.0	64.70
		LL ₅	9	158.8	0.539	152.4	0.461	63.7	24.7	48.49
		LL	10	84.9	0.148	118.6	0.852	112.0	****	****